

What is CryoEM ?

CryoEM is an electron microscopy technique allowing the observation of biological samples at very high resolution without altering their structure, thanks to freezing at very low temperatures.

What are the benefits of CryoEM ?

Observation of biological samples by electron microscopy at very low temperatures (close to absolute 0) prevents crystallization, and thereby preserves the sample structure in a frozen hydrated state.

This protects the sample from the alterations and artifacts often observed in conventional electron microscopy, caused by chemical fixation, dehydration or metallization processes.

Therefore, it is mainly used for imaging sensitive biological structures, such as proteins, viruses, molecular complexes, cells and cellular complexes. It enables biological samples to be observed in 2D and 3D, at higher resolution, whilst preserving sample integrity.

CryoEM in brief

In a nutshell, cryo electron microscopy stands out for its ability to preserve the structure of biological samples whilst observing them at high resolution and allowing for the reconstruction of protein structures up to atomic resolution. It is therefore an essential technique for structural and cellular biology research.